

Polysteganus undulosus Seventyfour seabream

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Bony Fish

Size: 120 cm Total Length

Distribution:

This species is endemic to the southeastern coast of southern Africa, with a current distribution ranging from Sodwana Bay to Cape Agulhas.

Importance:

Due to overexploitation, the Seventyfour seabream remains off-limits to both commercial and recreational fishing. It is currently listed as Critically Endangered on the IUCN Red List.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 22.71 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 3.02 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome Length: 0.75 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 97.6% [Single: 94.5%, Duplicated: 3.1%]

Assembly N50: 654.82 kilobases

Contig number: 8 207

Sample Contributor contact details:

Dr Gwynneth Matcher

South African Institute for Aquatic Biodiversity

g.matcher@saiab.nrf.ac.za

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